

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MQ-2 SENSOR IN FIRE DETECTION

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Annotation: *Fire detection is a crucial safety measure for both residential and industrial settings. Fire can cause serious damage to property and life, and it is important to detect it as early as possible and take appropriate actions. One of the devices that can help in fire detection is the MQ-2 sensor. The MQ-2 sensor is an electronic device that is used to detect various types of gases, including hydrogen (H₂), liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), methane (CH₄), carbon monoxide (CO), alcohol, smoke, and propane. It is widely used in both residential and industrial settings to detect gas leaks and prevent potential hazards. The MQ-2 sensor is also known as a chemiresistor. It contains a sensing material whose resistance changes when it comes in contact with the gas. This change in the value of resistance is used for the detection of gas.*

Key words: *AnnotaFire, detection, Safety, measure, Residential Industrial, settings, Property Life Detect Early Appropriate actions, MQ-2 sensor, Electronic device, Gases.*

Introduction

The MQ-2 sensor has four pins: A0, D0, GND, and VCC. The A0 pin outputs an analog signal that is proportional to the concentration of gas. The D0 pin outputs a digital signal that indicates whether the gas concentration has reached a certain threshold. The GND pin connects to the ground, and the VCC pin connects to a 5V power supply. The MQ-2 sensor works on the principle of adsorption. Adsorption is a process in which molecules of gas stick to the surface

of a solid material. The sensing material of the MQ-2 sensor is a metal oxide semiconductor, such as tin dioxide (SnO_2). When there is no gas present, the sensing material has a high resistance due to the lack of free electrons.

When the sensor is exposed to a gas, the gas molecules adsorb on the surface of the sensing material and react with oxygen ions. This reaction releases electrons, which reduce the resistance of the sensing material. The more gas molecules adsorb on the surface, the lower the resistance becomes. The resistance of the sensor is different depending on the type of gas. The MQ-2 sensor is sensitive to smoke and to the following flammable gases: LPG, butane, propane, methane, alcohol, and hydrogen³. The sensitivity of the sensor can be adjusted by using a potentiometer that changes the threshold value of the digital output. The MQ-2 sensor is important for fire detection because it can detect smoke and flammable gases that are often associated with fire. Smoke is a visible indication of fire, and flammable gases can cause explosions or fuel the fire. By detecting these gases, the MQ-2 sensor can alert users about a possible fire hazard and trigger appropriate actions, such as activating an alarm, turning off appliances, or calling emergency services. The MQ-2 sensor has several advantages for fire detection:

- It has a wide operating detection range;
- It has a fast response time;
- It has a low cost;
- It has a long lifespan;
- It has a simple interface with Arduino or other microcontrollers;

One of the ways to use the MQ-2 sensor for fire detection is to connect it with an Arduino board and some other components, such as LEDs and a buzzer. The Arduino board can read the analog or digital output from the sensor and perform

some actions based on the gas level.

For example, one can build a smoke detector that beeps when it detects flammable gas or smoke using the following components:

- 1 x MQ-2 gas sensor
- 1 x Arduino UNO
- 1 x breadboard
- 1 x red LED
- 1 x green LED
- 1 x buzzer
- 3 x 220 Ω resistor
- Jumper wires

The schematic for this project is shown below:

The code for this project can be found here:

```
int redLed = 12;
int greenLed = 11;
int buzzer = 10;
int smokeA0 = A5;
int sensorThres = 400;

void setup() {
  pinMode(redLed, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(greenLed, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(buzzer, OUTPUT);
  pinMode(smokeA0, INPUT);
  Serial.begin(9600);
}
```

```
void loop() {  
  int analogSensor = analogRead(smokeA0);  
  
  Serial.print("Pin A0: ");  
  Serial.println(analogSensor);  
  if (analogSensor > sensorThres)  
  {  
    digitalWrite(redLed, HIGH);  
    digitalWrite(greenLed, LOW);  
    tone(buzzer, 1000, 200);  
  }  
  else  
  {  
    digitalWrite(redLed, LOW);  
    digitalWrite(greenLed, HIGH);  
    noTone(buzzer);  
  }  
  delay(100);  
}
```

Conclusion

The MQ-2 sensor is an important device for fire detection because it can detect smoke and flammable gases that can cause or indicate fire. The sensor works by measuring the change in resistance of a metal oxide semiconductor when it comes in contact with gas. The sensor can be easily interfaced with Arduino or other microcontrollers to create fire detection systems that can alert users and take appropriate actions.

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